

Synthesis and antimicrobial properties of zinc-, cadmium- and mercury(II) complexes of sulfur donor ligands

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Manuscript received 7 December 1999, revised 19 June 2000, accepted 26 August 2000

The tridentate Schiff base sulfur donor ligand forms complexes with divalent Zn, Cd and Hg. The complexes are four-coordinated with a tetrahedral geometry around the metal ions. The mass spectral data also support the assigned metal and ligand ratios. Metal chelates are more toxic in comparison with ligand.

Benzimidazole derivatives possess various biological activities¹. Here, synthesis, characterisation and antimicrobial studies of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes of 1-methyl-2-acetylbenzimidazolethiosemicarbazone (MACBBZTSC) are reported.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are stable in air and nonhygroscopic. They are slightly soluble in methanol, ethanol, dioxane and fairly soluble in DMF and DMSO and insoluble in water. Their compositions are represented as $MLCl$, where $M = Zn^{II}$, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} , $L = 1$ -methyl-2-acetylbenzimidazolethiosemicarbazone. The low molar conductance values of the Zn, Cd, Hg complexes (10 , 8 and $12 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$, respectively) indicate their non-electrolytic nature² and all the complexes are monomers.

The IR ligand bands at 3435 and $3290 cm^{-1}$ are assigned to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations³ of free NH_2 group. These bands remained unaltered in the spectra of the complexes which indicates non-participation of NH_2 in coordination. The band at $3140 cm^{-1}$ due to imido group of thiosemicarbazide moiety, disappeared in the complex. It is evident that in the benzimidazole pyridine nitrogen can involve in the coordination⁴. The strong ligand band at $1610 cm^{-1}$ shifted by 10 – $20 cm^{-1}$ in the metal chelates, indicating coordination through azomethine nitrogen⁵. The ligand can undergo keto-enol tautomerism.

The ligand bands at 1278 and $860 cm^{-1}$ shifted to lower wavenumbers (1178 , $810 cm^{-1}$) in the complexes, indicat-

ing the change from $\nu_{C=S}$ to $C-S^6$. The thiol group (2590 – $2540 cm^{-1}$) is not observed in the spectrum⁷ of the complex which indicates the deprotonation of thiol to form a covalent bond between the sulfur and the metal ion. In the spectra of the complexes, the observed ν_{M-N} (420 – 500), ν_{M-S} (350 – 380) and ν_{M-Cl} (270 – 300) absorptions⁸ support the coordination of azomethine nitrogen, thio enol sulfur and chloride.

¹H NMR spectra : The ligand spectrum shows ¹H NMR signals at δ 10.4 (imido proton), 7.25 – 7.65 (aromatic protons), 7.5 (NH_2 protons of thiosemicarbazide moiety)⁹, 4.12 (*N*-methyl of benzimidazole moiety) and 2.5 (*C*-methyl protons). The NMR spectra of all the metal chelates indicate the presence of aromatic protons, NH_2 protons, *N*-methyl protons and *C*-methyl protons. This reveals that NH_2 protons are not deprotonated and do not participate in covalent bond formation with the metal ion. The signal at δ 10.4 (imido proton) of the ligand does not appear in the spectra of the metal chelates. This indicates that imido proton is shifted to enol form. The complex spectra do not show any peak near δ 4.0 ($S-H$), indicating the deprotonation of thiol group and involvement in the bond formation with metal ion.

The mass spectra of the ligand and metal chelates were recorded under liquid secondary ion mass (LSIM) spectral conditions¹⁰. The spectrum revealed m/z 248 as the base peak that corresponds to the $[(M + H)]^+$ ion of ligand and it confirms the assigned molecular weight¹¹ of the ligand. The mass spectrum of the Zn complex showed abundant ion at m/z 310 which corresponds to $[(ligand + Zn^{64}-H)]^+$ ion. This is due to the cleavage of complex to give the ion at m/z 310 to get net charge one (+1) on the species be-

cause monopositively charged ions only could be detected under LSIMS conditions used. The LSIMS of the Cd complexes resulted in the abundant ion at m/z 360, 396 and 607. The ion at m/z 360 corresponds to [(ligand + Cd¹¹⁴-H)]⁺, resulting from the decomposition of the metal complex. The ion at m/z 396 corresponds to [(L + CdCl)]⁺ ion. The ion represents the presence of chloride in the complex and during the formation of this ion hydrogen (thiol proton) is not lost. The peak at m/z 607 corresponds to [(2L + Cd-H)]⁺ ion. But this peak abundance is much less. The LSI mass spectrum of the mercury complex showed ions at m/z 448, 484 and 695. The ion at m/z 448 corresponds to [(ligand + Hg²⁰²-H)]⁺ ion. The ion at m/z 448 corresponds to [(L + Hg²⁺ Cl)]⁺ ion. The ion at m/z 695 found in the spectrum corresponds to [(2L + Hg-H)]⁺ ion. This indicates the metal ligand ratio as 1 : 2. But the abundance of the ion is much less. The mass spectral data of metal chelates support the metal ligand ratio as 1 : 1. On the basis of above discussion tetrahedral geometry is proposed for the Zn, Cd and Hg complexes¹².

Biological activity : The ligand MACBZTSC and its metal complexes were screened¹³ for antibacterial and antifungal activities against some of the pathogenic bacteria *B. subtilis*, *E. coli* and fungus *A. niger*. The results reveal that all the metal complexes are more toxic than the ligand.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

1-Methyl-2-acetylbenzimidazolethiosemicarbazone : A mixture of equimolar amounts of 1-methyl-2-acetylbenzimidazole and thiosemicarbazide in aqueous methanol containing a few drops of acetic acid, was refluxed for 3 h and then cooled. The resulting white solids¹⁴ (80%) were washed and crystallized from dioxane, m.p. 228–230⁰.

Synthesis of the complexes : To a solution of MACBZTSC in methanol (10 mmol), the metal chloride salt (10 mmol) dissolved in minimum amount of aqueous methanol was added and the mixture was refluxed for 2–3 h in neutral condition. The resulting complexes were washed with cold methanol and hot water and dried under reduced pressure over CaCl₂ (m.ps. >250⁰).

C, N and H were determined microanalytically at H.C.U., Hyderabad. Metals were estimated on a Hitachi Z-

6100 atomic absorption spectrometer. Chloride was estimated by using standard procedure¹⁵. Molar conductance of the complexes (in DMF at 1×10^{-3} M) was measured using a Digisun DI-909 conductivity meter at 25^o. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1430 and 337 spectrophotometers. NMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a JEOL FX-90 FT spectrometer using TMS as the reference and mass spectra on a V.G. Autospec spectrometer operating under liquid secondary ion mass spectral conditions (LSIMS).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. M. Vairamani and Dr. S. Prabhakar of Mass Spectrometry Center, I.I.C.T., Hyderabad, for providing the mass spectra. The authors are also thankful to Principal, J.N.T.U. College of Engineering, for facilities.

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